

e-ISSN: 3107-3956

Volume 08 Issue 01
Jan-April 2026

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Submission Date: Feb
26, 2026

Copyright Received
Date : Feb 26, 2026

Published Date: ***

Performance Evaluation of PVDF Hollow Fiber Membrane for Water Quality Improvement

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ABSTRACT

Water pollution is a major environmental problem because of Growing industrial & city developments. Wastewater contains solid, organic matter, bacteria & harmful chemicals from industries that reduce water quality. Solution to this problem is membrane technologies, especially PVDF (Polyvinylidene fluoride) hollow fiber membrane, and it has emerged as an effective method to treat wastewater. In this paper we discussed the performance, advantages, working principle & applications of PVDF hollow fiber membrane in improving wastewater quality. After using the PVDF hollow fiber membrane it provides high filtration efficiency, strong chemical resistance & long operational life also. Freshwater resources are decreasing because of the increasing discharge of wastewater from sources like industrial and domestic. Sedimentation, coagulation & sand filtration are traditional treatments, this treatment has limitation in removing the fine particles & microorganisms. We employ membrane filtering technology, an innovative treatment method, to get over this restriction. PVDF is extensively utilized due to its high mechanical strength, superior chemical resistance, thermal stability, and good permeability.

Keyword: PVDF, hollow fiber membrane, Ultra filtration, water treatment, membrane technology

INTRODUCTION

For both environmental preservation and human health, access to clean, safe water is crucial. Advanced treatment technologies are now required due to increased levels of toxins in water bodies caused by home wastewater, agricultural runoff, and industrial discharge. These contaminants reduce water quality and can cause serious risks to both human health and the environment. Traditional treatment methods such as sedimentation and sand filtration are not always sufficient to remove small particulates and dissolved pollutants effectively. Therefore, advanced water purification systems are required to ensure safe and maintain water quality.[1]

Membrane filtration is one of the most effective, modern and accurate method for water treatment. Membrane processes such as microfiltration, ultrafiltration, nanofiltration, and reverse osmosis offer high separation efficiency with compact system design and lower chemical consumption. Among various membrane materials, PVDF hollow fiber membranes are widely used due to their excellent chemical resistance, long-lasting quality, mechanical strength, thermal stability, and high flow rate. The hollow fiber structure provides a large surface area for filtration allowing effective removal of turbidity, Total suspended solids (TSS), chemical oxygen demand (COD), and biological oxygen demand (BOD). This study evaluates the performance of PVDF hollow fiber membrane by comparing treated water quality parameters with conventional Sewage Treatment Plant (STP) treated water.[2]

LITERATURE REVIEW

In order to reduce biofouling and provide antibacterial and antifouling capabilities, this study created a PVDF hollow fiber membrane combined with zinc oxide (ZnO). This modification improved membrane life and performance in

wastewater treatment, also increased surface wettability which is contributed to improved filtration efficiency. R. Kamaludin et al. (2022)[3]

This study focused on enhancing the performance of PVDF ultrafiltration meters by modifying them with nanocomposite hydrogels. The modified membranes should improve hydraulic performance and anticlogging properties and minimize contaminant accumulation during operation leading to better water purification efficiency. A. Ghobadi Moghadam et al. (2023)[4]

This study introduced a polyamide/polyvinylidene fluoride (PA/ PVDF) hollow fiber nanofiltration membrane that exhibited high filtration rate and selective rejection of calcium ions and antibiotics, making it suitable for advance drinking water purification by removing hardness and micropollutants from water. Y. Tang et al. (2024)[5]

The researchers developed a hydrophilic PVDF hollow fiber membrane designed for separating dissolved organic contaminants from highly saline wastewater. These modifications enhanced the membranes mechanical stability and performance in challenging water conditions, making it suitable for industrial wastewater treatment. S. Oppong et al. (2025)[6]

The researchers investigated the preparation of high performance PVDF hollow fiber membranes by integrating with SiO₂ particles followed by acid and alkaline surface conditioning the study aim to improved water permeability and separation efficiency. These techniques improved porosity, mechanical integrity, and permeate flow rate. C. Hou et al (2025)[7]

METHODOLOGY

Materials and Water Characterization

Sample collection

Water samples were collected from the selected source and stored in clean, contamination-free containers. This is important because even minor contamination can affect test results.[8]

Parameters tested

The following key water quality parameters were measured:

- pH → Indicates acidity or alkalinity of water
- Total Suspended Solids (TSS) → Measures suspended salts and minerals
- Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) → Indicates total organic pollution
- Biological Oxygen Demand (BOD) → Shows biodegradable organic matter
- Turbidity → Measures water clarity (suspended particles)

Membrane Module and Experimental

setup

Membrane type

A PVDF (Polyvinylidene Fluoride) hollow fiber membrane was used because:

- It has high chemical resistance
- It is widely used in water filtration
- It provides good separation efficiency

Membrane cleaning

Before each experiment:

- The membrane was washed with distilled water
- This removes previously deposited particles and avoids experimental errors
- Schematic Diagram (Fig. 1): Shows components such as:
- Feed tank
- Pump
- Membrane module
- Permeate collection unit

Fig. 1: Schematic Diagram of Water Treatment System.

Process

- Feed water is passed through the membrane module
- Clean water (permeate) is collected at the outlet

Sample

- Permeate samples were collected at **regular time intervals**
- This helps track performance over time

Analysis

- Same parameters (pH, TDS, COD, BOD, turbidity) were tested again
- This allows comparison with initial values

Consistency

- All experiments were performed under **identical conditions**

- This ensures results are reliable and comparable

Performance Evaluation

The removal efficiency (R, %) of each parameter was calculated using following equation: $R (\%) = (C_i - C_f) * 100 / C_i$

Where ,
 C_i is the initial concentration of

parameters in feed water and C_f is the concentration of parameter in the permeate in the permeate after membrane filtration.

Each experiment was carried out in triplicate, and average values were reported. The results were tabulated and compared to analyze the efficiency, stability, and suitability of the membrane for water treatment applications.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Parameters	STP Value	PVDF Value
pH	6.9	7.2
BOD (mg/L)	8.8	35
COD (mg/L)	60	80
TSS / Turbidity (mg/L)	14	5

The performance of the PVDF hollow fiber membrane was evaluated by comparing the treated water quality parameters obtained from the Sewage Treatment Plant (STP) and the PVDF membrane filtration system. The main parameters analyzed were pH, COD, BOD, and Turbidity.

pH Analysis

The pH value of STP-treated water was 6.9, while the PVDF membrane-treated water showed a pH of 7.2. The slight increase indicates that the membrane filtration process maintains balanced condition.

Biological Oxygen Demand (BOD)

The STP-treated water showed a BOD value of 8.8 mg/L, while the PVDF membrane-treated sample showed 35 mg/L. An increase in BOD value after membrane filtration may indicate the presence of dissolved biodegradable organic matter that was not completely removed, or possible variation in sampling conditions.

Chemical Oxygen Demand

The COD value increased from 60 mg/L

(STP) to 80 mg/L in PVDF-treated sample. This variation may be assigned to differences in sampling conditions, membrane fouling, or concentration polarization during filtration.

TSS / Turbidity (mg/L)

A significant improvement was observed in TSS/ Turbidity reduction. The STP effluent showed a value of 14mg/L, whereas the PVDF membrane reduced it to 5 mg/L. This indicates the excellent solid-liquid separation capability of hollow fiber membrane.

Overall, the results demonstrate that the PVDF hollow fiber membrane is highly effective in reducing turbidity and suspended solids, while maintaining stable pH levels. While variations were observed in BOD and COD values, optimization of operational parameters improve overall treatment performance. These results suggest that PVDF membranes have strong potential for advanced wastewater treatment and water quality improvement applications

CONCLUSION

PVDF hollow fiber membranes improve water quality by removing dirt, suspended particles, and harmful microorganisms. As a result, the PVDF filtered water has very low turbidity and looks clear as compared to STP treated water. These membranes show good water flow (flux) during operation, however over time, the flow rate can decrease because of fouling caused by organic matter and bio fouling. Therefore, proper pretreatment and regular cleaning is required. The membrane can recover well after cleaning and are durable, but surface modifications can future improve their long-term performance and sustainability. While PVDF membranes are very effective in removing physical impurities and microbes, they are less effective in removing dissolved organic substances. As a costing point of view municipal STP are expensive but suitable for large-scale wastewater management, whereas PVDF membrane systems are more economical for small or localized treatment applications.

FUTURE SCOPE

PVDF membrane can be modified with nano particles like TiO₂, Ag, Graphene oxide to enhance anti-microbial and antifouling properties. In future this technology can be used to purify sea water due to their chemical resistance. It can develop hybrid system with UV treatment and activated carbon. The PVDF material can be used for scaling up for small scale industries and municipal wastewater

recycling. More research can be explored environmentally friendly manufacturing and disposal of chemical contaminated water. In future design may focus on less energy consumption, low pressure and gravity driven or solar energy also can be used.

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